

Scientific Aesthetics

From Idealist Philosophy to Experimental Aesthetics and the Foundations of Modernism

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Abstract

From 1848 a new independent type of thinking, free from authority, was becoming increasingly popular.¹ This type of thinking oriented itself to the methods of the natural sciences. More and more the natural sciences prevailing over speculation. Two specific expressions of this development were the conceptions, by Gustav Fechner, of psychophysics and a new scientific aesthetics.

But the new scientific aesthetics equally took away authority from academic philosophy and placed this authority as Fechners work critiques the hierarchical, elitist tone of idealist philosophy. Psychophysics as Lorain Daston writes, was considered by some “as a threat to the traditional bases of morality”² Or as she writes in her book *Objectivity* “Armed with cameras, collimators, chronometers, and calipers, scientists studied the speed of nervous transmission, color sensations, attention spans, and even logic and mathematics as psychophysiological phenomena.”³

According to Michael Pauen, these new approaches to Aesthetics had a profound influence on the aesthetics of modernity, although there have been only few and incomplete attempts to trace this genealogy.⁴ Thus, it are psychophysics and Scientific aesthetics which, I argue, have contributed to that which is understood as modern, even though its own traces have largely faded.

1 Lassewitz, *G. Th. Fechner*, 66

2 Daston, *British Responses to Psycho-Physiology, 1860-1900*, 192

3 Daston, *Objectivity*, 258

4 Pauen, *Die Wissenschaft vom Schönen. Kunstpsychologie und die Ästhetik der Moderne*, 75

Introduction

This text reconstructs the emergence of scientific aesthetics in the nineteenth century and examines its role in shaping the epistemic foundations of modern art and architecture. Focusing on Gustav Fechner's psychophysics and the concept of association, it traces how aesthetic experience came to be understood as a measurable, empirical phenomenon rather than a purely philosophical one.

The argument proceeds in three steps. First, it situates scientific aesthetics within a broader critique of idealist philosophy, particularly in relation to Kant's marginalisation of association. Second, it follows the institutionalisation and dissemination of psychophysical research from Leipzig into wider European contexts. Third, it analyses how these ideas entered artistic and architectural discourse through interdisciplinary exchanges, congresses, and pedagogical institutions.

Experimental Aesthetics

When, in 1920 the first issue of *L'Esprit Nouveau*, published by Le Corbusier and Amadee Ozenfant, the magazines overarching objective was, according to the architectural historian, Judi Loach, articulated as the development of an "experimental aesthetic".⁵ But already the decades towards the end of the twentieth century, many "psychophysical" laboratories were established in Europe and the late nineteenth century was marked by an "invasion [...] of aesthetics by natural science", or an "esthétique scientifique."⁶

A society which regards itself as being in a state of revolution tends to break away from old social conventions and create fashions, gestures and a language more suitable to its new condition. This is what happens, when a conflux of technical evolution brings into motion a whole set of social and intellectual disruptions. This is why psychology and especially associations with history and meaning were so relevant for the modern Avant-Garde around the turn towards the twentieth century. Peter Behrens, Kandinsky and Le Corbusier were out of genuine interest, opportunism, or at least for polemic reasons, at least marginally occupied with the associative value of perception and especially a new *scientific or empirical aesthetics*, which established at the end of the nineteenth century, but becomes to take central.

In 1876, at the age of 74, Fechner published *Vorschule der Ästhetik* (1876) "Zur experimentellen

5 Loach, "Architecture, science and purity", in *Being Modern*, 216 (In 1920, the Sorbonne inaugurated an Aesthetics Chair, which was formally titled the "Chair of Aesthetics and the Science of Art.")

6 Brain, *The Pulse of Modernism. Physiological Aesthetics in Fin-de-Siècle Europe*, 95

Ästhetik” a book on experimental aesthetics, also referred to as “wissenschaftliche Ästhetik” (scientific aesthetics), or “ästhetik von unten.” which signifies an empirical, non-theoretical approach to understanding beauty, by drawing knowledge from experiments, inductively and gather data, to derive from them general principles. The term “von unten” captures its empirical orientation, but also conveys a non-dogmatic attitude towards science. It could be speculated that the terminology implies a certain social equality and that it is a playful provocation towards established philosophical doctrines, to not attempt to explain beauty from a single theoretical perspective, in a time where aesthetics was still very much influenced by German idealism and thus a matter of deductions from idealised principles and concepts, such as the beautiful, or the sublime, articulated by philosophers such as Hegel and Kant.⁷ Yet, he did not seek to replace traditional philosophy with his methods, but add to it a method which started to think from the other direction.

Before turning his attention to aesthetics, the physiologist Gustav Fechner established a new scientific direction, which would become popular throughout Europe: Psychophysics. Just as Experimental Aesthetics sought to quantify sensations of beauty, Psychophysics sought to quantify Psychology, and thus his work belonged to a larger development of scientists and thinkers who sought to establish science on more factual and methodological Foundations. Psychophysics which posits that external stimuli have a direct and measurable effect.

In extension to this he established a new scientific aesthetics, which used quantitative methods to measure the effects of and associations between form, sound and colour.

Fechner on Association

At a conference in 1866, at the Leipziger Kunstverein, Gustav Theodor Fechner (1801 - 1887), a young psychologist was ridiculed by professional philosophers, after talking about association and it where the laymen whose interest he caught. For this discrediting of association as an epistemological category, and the minor interest it got as object of scientific study as a result, Fechner blames Kant:

„Wie bemerkt, trägt hauptsächlich Kant die Schuld der verbreiteten Ansicht, daß der assoziative Faktor nur eine unwesentliche Zutat zum Eindrucke der reinen oder nach Kants Ausdruck "freien" Schönheit sei, für welche Zutat er den Ausdruck "anhängende"

⁷ Fechner, *Elemente der Psychophysik*. 10

Schönheit hat; dieser aber schreibt er keine eigentliche ästhetische Bedeutung zu. [...] Kant hat in seiner Lehre von der sog. anhängenden Schönheit des Prinzips nur gedacht, um es in Sachen der reinen Schönheit außer Kredit zu bringen, hat seine Nachfolger darin gefunden, und nachdem man es von dieser Seite für abgetan erklärt, hat man sich auch von dieser Seite nicht weiter darum gekümmert.”⁸

The Harvard psychologist Howard Warren (1867 – 1934) observed that “German writers treat the association movement very inadequately, on account of the overshadowing influence of Kant and his school on German thought.”⁹ He described a tendency of German thinkers to see the “the rational faculty as unanalysable and self validating”¹⁰, attributing a larger importance to “innate factors”¹¹. Where-association psychologists persist in a stronger malleability brought forward by external factors, as a logical consequence of the rules of association.

This contrast becomes even more apparent when examining the position of Johann Friedrich Herbart (1776 - 1841), a pessimist on the philosophical progress since Kant. He compared the possible consequences of his transcendental philosophy with fatalism¹² - which ought to destabilise the untrained thinker.¹³ Herbart acknowledged the pedagogical potential of association – a viewpoint, which is somewhat contrary to Kants rejection of epistemological value of association. Association becomes an essential component in his Didactic theory, which he starts from an empirical, inductive foundation.¹⁴ For Herbart everything is in flow, and the scientific imagination in particular profits from the convergence and recombinations of thoughts, helped through, analysis, method and system.¹⁵ Thus although he also sees a philosophers task in purging language of “irrelevant associations”¹⁶, he acknowledges it as a value phenomena in the process of learning.

He declared the beginning of a scientific enquiry into the subject of mental associations. An enquiry which arguably has been made into reality by subsequent psychologists.

“Eine Untersuchung von großer Wichtigkeit steht bevor; die nicht bloss dasjenige unter sich befasst, was gewöhnlich mit dem Namen der Association belegt wird, sondern die

8 G. T. Fechner, *Vorschule der Aesthetik*, 86

9 Warren, *A History of the Association Psychology*, 20

10 Warren, *A History of the Association Psychology*, 9

11 Warren, *A History of the Association Psychology*, 20

12 Herbart, *Umriss pädagogischer Vorlesungen*, 3

13 Herbart, *Sämmtliche Werke. 10. Schriften zur Pädagogik*, 213

14 Herbart, *Sämmtliche Werke. 10. Schriften zur Pädagogik*, 92

15 Herbart, *Sämmtliche Werke. 10. Schriften zur Pädagogik*, 50

16 Beisler, *Johann Friedrich Herbart. Grandfather of Analytic Philosophy*, 103

mit ihren Folgen tief in die, durch falsche Metaphysik verdunkelten, Fragen von den Formen der Erfahrung hineingreift.”¹⁷

To understand Fechners critique we have to look at Kant. Kant in his critique of pure reason had put forward the ideas of schema and apperception to deal with the inadequacies of pure association. Kant criticizes among many things, the direct deduction of thoughts from things. He comments that there is something participating in our understanding of objects: the concepts (Begriffe), or better lexical entities with which they are thought of. He separates clearly between ideas (Ideen) and concepts (Begriffe). A pure objective understanding is not possible, without the participation of concepts. Kant therefore declares ideas to be subjective by nature and not objective as the language of the English empiricists suggests.

Kant reduces the significance of the rules of association to purely subjective phenomenon and therefore Kant ignores rules of association to have any philosophical task, they do not contribute to the question of a possibility of a priori knowledge and belong, therefore, to the field of psychology. Although Kant does not see much purpose for association in the clarification of epistemological questions, he does see their potential to surpass beyond the scope of „natural“ experience. They help form aesthetic ideas. This associative imagination (Einbildungskraft or produktives Erkenntnisvermögen) can extend and expand conceptual understanding beyond that which can be grasped within the meaning of a single concept.¹⁸ Association can „move“ intellectual ideas. But contrary to empiricists, Kant considers the imagination itself to be an a priori quality of all human beings bound to its own subjective rules of apperception.¹⁹ Apperception describes the confluence of impression and replaces many functions that association took in empiricist theories. Perhaps Kants most devastating and consequential critique, is that the association of ideas, lacks schema. This lack of schema and the concept of apperception become important topics for psychology in the centuries to come.

Kant proposed, association to be a matter for psychologists, not philosophers and this had made the topic unpopular among intellectuals. Kant tried to delineate philosophy from other professions, and determined that metaphysics should be the principal concern of philosophy. To the metaphysicians, aesthetic being would be a cornerstone of Kants encompassing system. This resulted in a philosophical pondering, which would later attract criticism.

Following Kants transcendental meditations, Einfühlung becomes one of the more central

17 Herbart, *Psychology als Wissenschaft*, 289

18 E. Kant, *Kritik der Urteilskraft*, 251

19 E. Kant, *Kritik der reinen Vernunft*, 182 a

concept in German idealism. A projection of subjectivity onto the object, as embodiment of an idea outside the object.²⁰ In 1898 Paul Stern publishes a small book on the aesthetic discourse between proponents of the metaphysical and the psychological school, which both try to explain how people are “touched” emotionally by experience. Those of the metaphysical school propose empathy (Einfühlung), whereas the psychological school proposes the concept of association. A few like Jean Paul, see validity in both. Empathy theory starts reasoning from the projective sentiment of the subject, compared to the empirical school, which starts thinking from objects. This is a response to Kant's criticism against the empirical school. Empiricists, such as Hume and Locke had built their model of subjectivity on objective experiences. Kant had differentiated much more clearly between the objectivity of things and the subjectivity of experience. From this, comes the notion that an aesthetic experience is the result of a projective emotional cast, and not a result of a series of objective impressions, associatively connected.

In Paul Stern's text, the metaphysical school is represented by - among others - Johannes Immanuel Volkelt (1848-1930). Lotze himself was sceptical of the association theory, however, and regarded investigations into the laws and modes of association as a profitless task. For Friedrich Vischer objects themselves become symbolical, which relate to and activate an inner symbolic world. This symbolism allowed both metaphysical and psychological interpretations of experience. His son, Robert Vischer develops Einfühlung as the most essential concept to describe the mechanism behind aesthetic experiences.

Fechner's opinion of the aesthetic importance of association was not completely dissimilar to Kant's, he also distinguished between primary and secondary experiences. Although he sees these secondary qualities as having immediate effect on aesthetic judgement. Fechner argues that people see the thing itself immediately with its associated meaning. Fechner describes associations as a web, where if one localised region is touched, its vibrations bring a series of connected emotions into movement, which influence the initial experience. He brings the example of a crown, whose function and symbolic meaning are observed immediately. Separating thing and associated meaning is an intellectual and effortful act. A similar effect counts for building styles, and the relationship between part and whole. He argues that there are associations between members and the impression of the whole, who make the impression of a style being more or less a suitable. A similar process which is at play with the invention of hybrid animals, such as Sphinx, centaurs, etc.

²⁰ P. Stern, *Einfühlung und Association in der neueren Ästhetik*, 7

Leipzig and the dissemination of psychology

Wundt followed in Fechners footsteps in is regarded as the father of psychology. He considered associations from the perspective of learning process and cultural evolution. Wundt influenced discourse on symbolism, meaning, language and culture in a wider sense. Wundts students on the other hand would continue to establish new research institutes elsewhere and they would write important theoretical works, and engage in academic discussions that are still relevant today.

Towards the end of the twentieth century, research on mental associations shifted from the United Kingdom to Germany, with Leipzig emerging as a leading centre for psychological research. The two primary figures in this regard are Gustav Fechner and Wilhelm Wundt.

Leipzig is usually pinpointed as the city that housed the first experimental laboratories. This shift was also one from speculative philosophy to the exact sciences and it also meant that the study of mental associations became predominantly studied in Leipzig. As psychology involves the study of perception and the measurements of mental processes, these also influenced discourse on aesthetics. And many influential discussions of this time have intellectual links to psychology and the discourses with which it was occupied. Thus, at the beginning of the twentieth century questions regarding beauty became seen, not as something to be solved as a philosophical problem alone, but as a problem which should be engaged with the aid of exact methods of observation and statistics.

Both Fechner, Wundt and Leipzig in general exerted international influence, through the students they educated, their publications and the many books and essays written about their work. Fechner changed psychology and Wundts laboratory educated many students that would become important names not only in psychology but many adjacent fields. Often with the concept of association in a position of fundamental significance. Fechner and Wundt's work laid the foundations for modern psychology and its influence extended far beyond, shaping disciplines like sociology, aesthetics, linguistics, and art history across Europe.²¹

Karl Lamprecht a friend of Wundt, and Historian in Leipzig started to see history from a psychological perspective: “a new period” is also one of new psychic existence, a new “psychic existence” which is determined “the vast extension of association and stimuli which arise from the new technical, economic, and social culture..”²² While Warburg, saw symbols are not the end products of psychic energy, but operative elements within a “psychophysical process”, capable of feeding back into and reshaping perception and experience.²³

21 For Instance Durkheim, who, for a short time studied under Wundt.

22 Lamprecht, *What is History?*, 28

23 Warburg, Sandro Botticellis „Geburt der Venus," 25

The dissemination

The institutional consolidation of psychology created the conditions for interdisciplinary exchange. These exchanges became particularly visible in international congresses, where aesthetic theory, empirical research, and artistic practice intersected. . First, laboratories inspired on those in Leipzig, where founded at the Sorbonne. Here psychology, but also aesthetics was studied after the model of Wundts laboratory. A few decades later, congresses such as the “Kongress für Allgemeine Kunstwissenschaften” - which aimed at unifying the scientific study of art - functioned as nodes. Here influential academics from different countries, especially France and Germany, but also different disciplines met. In 1914, at one of such congresses in Berlin, the Franco-German philosopher Victor Basch would attend and discuss with Peter Behrens the utilitarian aesthetics of the new age.²⁴ Peter Behrens had employed Le Corbusier, while Victor Basch would later write an introduction to *L'Esprit Nouveau*, which was first published in 1920. But also in Russia, shortly after the October revolution a, a psychophysical laboratory was was instituted under the directorship of Kandinsky in Moscow at the GaChN. Kandinsky would later work at the Bauhaus, where he taught under the directorship of Walter Gropius, another former employer of Peter Behrens.

These places facilitates a flow of information between disciplines, and were places where the idea of Art, not as something subjective, or purely theoretical, but as scientific and empirical were explored. In this respect they had an indirect, small, but significant effect on art and architecture.

Allgemeine Kunstwissenschaften

The interdisciplinary ambitions of scientific aesthetics become most explicit at the moment when its methods leave the laboratory and enter broader cultural discourse. The 1913 Congress for Aesthetics and General Art Studies can be read as precisely such a moment: an attempt to stabilise a shared language between empirical research and aesthetic theory.

Just before the outbreak of the first world war the “Kongress für Ästhetik und Allgemeine Kunstwissenschaft,” was organised by Max Dessoir, a psychologist and philosopher, an held between 7. and 9. October 1913 in Berlin. It was an effort to bring together philosophical and

²⁴ Translation by the Author

psychological views on aesthetics, or theory and empirical methods as well as a broader interdisciplinary and international group of academics from sociology, anthropology, education, history and the arts to unify the study of aesthetics.²⁵ Themes were viewed from psychological, theoretical, but also from cultural and evolutionary perspectives and were especially influenced by the psychology of Wundt and Fechner, as well as the advent objective methods in general. Central to this effort was a push towards scientific rigor in art research, moving beyond metaphysical art theories dominant in the 19th century.²⁶

Different contributions discussed the contemporary state of experimental aesthetics. And many contributions took interdisciplinary positions, combining psychology, evolution and art. According to Dessoir, Art and aesthetics can not be explained purely in terms of beauty as aesthetical judgements are products of the mind, created within a cultural and historical context. Due to the development of an independent experimental psychology, it is necessary to create a forum where it could come into contact with philosophical thinking.

Further topics sociological aesthetics, music, primitive art, ornament, artistic intuition, often viewed within a particular psychological framework. There were contributions from Karl Lamprecht, Wundts Colleague in Leipzig, as well as Aby Warburg. Wilhelm Worringer - a proponent of abstraction - talked about the early developments of ornament and August Schwarsow held a presentation about spatial design as the essence of architectural creation.²⁷

In many of the contributions, Fechners concepts of the direct and indirect aesthetic experiences were at least a peripheral theme. Kaarle S. Laurila's presentation *Die assoziativen Faktoren des ästhetischen Eindrucks* (The Associative Factors of Aesthetic Impression) criticised earlier theories for their vague use of the term "association." He proposed that associations relevant to aesthetics should not simply refer to any idea linked in the mind but should involve connections that possess a certain logical coherence.

An interesting contribution was made by Peter Behrens, the proto-modernist - in whose office had worked Walter Gropius, Ludwig Mies van der Rohe and Le Corbusier. He gave a lecture about the relationship between technical culture and artistic creations. Behrens argued that while technological advancements had significantly improved material living standards, they have not yet achieved a full integration of technical and cultural (or spiritual) values.²⁸

25 Vorgeschichte in *Kongress für Ästhetik und Allgemeine Kunstwissenschaft: Berlin, 7.–10. Oktober 1913*, 1

26 Collenberg-Plotnikov, *Die Allgemeine Kunstwissenschaft (1906–1943)*, 9

27 Flach, *Die Wissenskünste der Avantgarden. Kunst, Wahrnehmungswissenschaften und Medien 1915-1930*, 60

28 Behrens, "Über den Zusammenhang des baukünstlerischen Schaffens mit der Technik" in *Kongress für Ästhetik und Allgemeine Kunstwissenschaft: Berlin, 7.–10. Oktober 1913*, 251

“I find it a disruption of aesthetic enjoyment in one of Berlin’s most beautiful new buildings that a discord remains in this regard: the West wing of the Wertheim building at Leipziger Platz, designed entirely in a medieval style, does nothing to suggest the bustle and activity of a department store behind its solemn and severe architecture. Even if this dissonance is solely based on the associative factor in aesthetic judgment, it nevertheless leads me to conclude that the demand for expressive alignment with purpose in architecture cannot be entirely dismissed.”²⁹

The passage touches on a key debate in aesthetics, particularly relevant at the time: should architecture primarily reflect the functional purpose of a building, or can it adhere to an aesthetic style disconnected from that function? Behrens suggests that the association between architectural form and purpose—what the building "expresses" versus what it actually is—creates a dissonance. This concept is rooted in the "associative factor" in aesthetics, which considers how our experiences and expectations influence our aesthetic judgements.

The Reception of Psychophysics in France and Russian

In late 19th-century France, the new scientific psychology developed in Germany began to take root and rapidly influence French intellectual life. In France and Russia, the concept of association is reconfigured in relation to questions of symbolism, form, and artistic production, thereby extending its function beyond psychology into concrete aesthetic practice.

From 1885 Théodule Ribot introduced British and German psychology to France, through several publications, and established psychology as an academic science.³⁰ In 1888, Théodule Ribot (1839–1916) was officially appointed to the Chair of Experimental and Comparative Psychology at the Collège de France. This appointment, which took place on February 18, marked the first formal recognition of the new scientific psychology in France.

At the Sorbonne, a *Laboratoire de psycho-physiologie* existed from 1889. A *Laboratoire de physiologie des sensations* was established a few years later in 1897.³¹ Charles Henry, spend most of his life as librarian. In he published an *Introduction à une esthétique scientifique*, in, 1885 and “*Esthétique et psychophysique*” in 1890. In reference to Fechner, Charles Henry developed a colour

29 Behrens, “Zusammenhang: d. baukünstler. Schaffens m. d. Technik” in *Kongress für Ästhetik und Allgemeine Kunstwissenschaft: Berlin, 7.–10. Oktober 1913*, 260

30 Ribot, *The Creative Imagination*, 1 He made theoretical contributed to the discourse on associations with theories on the evolution of general ideas and the creative imagination.

31 Kuehni, *The Scientific Aesthetic of Charles Henry*, 210 The laboratory of experimental psychology (1889) was attached to the « Ecole Pratique des Hautes Etudes » (EPHE) and was established in the Sorbonne.

circle: circular array of spectrum colours, starting with red at the top and moving clockwise to violet, with non-spectral purples closing the circle. Complementary colours are arranged opposite of each other, and pure spectral hues are located halfway between the centre and edge, fading towards white at the centre and black at the edge. This two-dimensional map of colour space, based on inner necessity and biological activity, provided painters with a clear method to create uplifting or depressing effects in their work.³² Allegedly this inspired Seurat, a friend of Henry to paint a series of paintings where he applied the theory. In 1910 obtained a position at the Sorbonne as director of *Laboratoire de physiologie des sensations*.

In 1908 Charles Lalo, a writer on aesthetics. published his “L'esthétique expérimentale de Fechner” in 1908 and “L'Esthétique Scientifique” in 1909. The essay ultimately calls for the development of a more comprehensive scientific aesthetics that respects the complexity of beauty and integrates insights from various disciplines. In 1912 Victor Basch, a lecturer in German language and literature at the Faculty of Letters in Paris and major figure in aesthetics at the Sorbonne became an important node in the exchange between German and French intellectuals.³³ He introduced German *ästhetics* in an essay called “Les grands courants de l'esthétique allemande contemporaine”.³⁴

The congress was also important due to its international connections, especially due to contributions from Charles Lalo who helped introduce German psychological aesthetics into France together with Victor Basch who would later write the introduction to *L'Esprit Nouveau*.

In 1920 the first issue of *L'Esprit Nouveau*, published by Le Corbusier and Amadee Ozenfant. The magazine's overarching objective was, according to Judi Loach, articulated as the development of an “experimental aesthetic”.³⁵ It had an introductory article written by Victor Basch, in which he introduced German scientific aesthetics, especially that of Fechner and Wundt.³⁶ Charles Henry contributed with an article: “La lumière, la couleur et la forme” in 1921.

The influence of German psychology went directly, radiating from the psychological institute in Leipzig, as well as directly from Fechner. Shortly after the October Revolution, the INKhUK was established as an overarching institution, of which Kandinsky would inhabit the chair of *Psychophysical* research.³⁷ The assignment of the Psychophysical department was, to „investigate

32 Kuehni, *The Scientific Aesthetic of Charles Henry*, 211

33 Halbwachs, *On Collective Memory*, 6

34 Loach, *Le Corbusier and the Creative Use of Mathematics*, 197 (A typographic mistake seems to have been made in this source, as it states it to be 1928, a number contradicted by other sources)

35 Loach, “Architecture, science and purity”, in *Being Modern*, 216 (In 1920, the Sorbonne inaugurated an Aesthetics Chair, which was formally titled the “Chair of Aesthetics and the Science of Art.”.)

36 Basch, “L'Esthétique Nouvelle et la Science de l'Art,” *L'Esprit Nouveau*, no. 1, 5

37 Podzemskaia, “Die Kunsttheorie Wassily Kandinskys und die Anfänge der GACHN,” in *Kunst als Sprache* -

the internal positive laws according to which artworks in each individual art field are created.“³⁸ A similar orientation towards experimental sciences was also prevalent at GACHN, where a psychophysical laboratory was established by Kandinsky as well. These experimental institutions, especially INKhUK coordinated the education at VKhUTEMAS and had a direct influence on the pedagogical methods used to educate architects.

According to Bernadette-Plotnikov the Allgemeine Kunstwissenschaften was a prototypical example for the interdisciplinary approaches at the State Academy of Art Sciences (GACHN)³⁹

A Student of Wundt, Münsterberg and what could be called the practical application of *psychophysics: psychotechnics* became a popular discipline at the time, as it was to aid in the organisation of an industrialised and rational society. For instance the teacher at VkhUTEMAS, Nikolai Ladovski, started a psychotechnical laboratory. And Russian Cinematographers visited Pavlovs laboratory, when, in 1925, Kuleshov and Pudovkin, worked on a short documentary titled *Mechanics of the Brain*.

In these contexts, scientific aesthetics is no longer a theoretical programme, but a set of techniques, pedagogies, and design principles. The transition from concept to practice marks the point at which its influence on modernism becomes most tangible.

Conclusion

The preceding sections have shown how scientific aesthetics emerged, institutionalised, and circulated across Europe. The conclusion draws these strands together to assess its broader significance for modernity.

By shifting attention from speculative deduction to empirical observation, figures like Fechner and Wundt reframed aesthetic experience as measurable, associative, and historically conditioned. This epistemic shift enabled aesthetics to circulate across disciplines and national contexts where it informed emerging practices in art and architecture. Even where its explicit traces faded, its methodological legacy persisted, shaping modernism's claim to objectivity, experimentation, and the systematic analysis of perception.

Gustav Theodor Fechner's psychophysics and experimental aesthetics, together with the research

Sprachen der Kunst. Russische Ästhetik und Kunsttheorie der 1920er Jahre in der europäischen Diskussion, 179

38 Plotnikov, "Einleitung : Die Staatliche Akademie der Kunstwissenschaften in der europäischen ästhetischen Diskussion der 1920er Jahre", in *Kunst als Sprache - Sprachen der Kunst. Russische Ästhetik und Kunsttheorie der 1920er Jahre in der europäischen Diskussion*, 12

39 Collenberg-Plotnikov, *Die Allgemeine Kunstwissenschaft (1906–1943)*, 9

tradition they inspired in Leipzig and beyond, marked a decisive shift in modern thought. By replacing speculative idealist philosophy with empirical, quantitative methods, they transformed the understanding of beauty, perception, and meaning from metaphysical deduction to measurable psychological processes.

This scientific approach to aesthetics profoundly influenced the historical avant-garde. From Peter Behrens and Le Corbusier in Western Europe to Kandinsky and the Russian constructivist institutions (INKhUK and VKhUTEMAS), the ideas of psychophysical research and associative perception helped shape an art and architecture that sought to align form with psychological effect, function, and modern life. Although the explicit traces of “scientific aesthetics” have largely faded, it remains embedded in what we understand as modernity.

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